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Reliable Methodology for Measuring SERS Enhancement Factor on Colloidal and Solid Substrates: A Practical Guide

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a robust and practical methodology for quantifying the Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) Enhancement Factor (EF) on both colloidal and solid substrates. SERS, a powerful technique for enhancing the Raman signals of analytes near plasmonic surfaces, has found extensive applications in fields such as biomedicine and materials science. However, inconsistencies in EF measurement methods have hindered cross-comparisons between different SERS substrates. This work addresses these challenges by providing a standardized protocol for EF determination for a wide variety of substrates composed of gold and silver nanoparticles, as well as nanostructured surfaces. Using p-mercaptobenzoic acid (p-MBA) as a model non-resonant probe, the approach accounts for key variables including substrate geometry, sampling volume, and substrate inhomogeneity. This reliable and reproducible method offers a practical framework for researchers to assess the performance of SERS substrates with simple instruments and techniques that should be easily available in a Raman spectroscopy laboratory.

1 | Introduction

Since its discovery dating back to 1974 [1], surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) has allowed not only the exploration of fundamental science at the nanoscale but has also made great strides in the development of sensing techniques in biomedicine, materials science, and environmental chemistry [2–5]. In its essentials, SERS relies on the amplification of the Raman signals of an analyte when adsorbed, or covalently linked, to a suitable substrate. Such a substrate may be identified by the ability of rising extremely intense local electromagnetic fields, or to influence the transition polarizability of the analyte by means of new quantum states derived by its interaction with

the supporting surface [6]. These are referred to as the two enhancement mechanisms in SERS, namely the Electromagnetic Enhancement (EME), in which a plasmonic substrate is needed, and the Chemical Enhancement (CE) [2]. The EME is found to be orders of magnitude more effective than CE in SERS, indeed electing the plasmonic substrates (nanostructured metal Au and Ag for instance) as the reference materials for SERS. In plasmonics, incident electromagnetic radiation excites free electrons in a metal's conduction band, causing them to form a polarizable “plasma plume.” However, these electrons are influenced by the positive nuclei, which act as a restoring force, pulling the electrons back toward equilibrium. In metals like gold and silver, the real part of the refractive index is negative

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in the visible range, which, combined with nanoscale morphology, results in low-order multipolar plasmons (mainly dipolar or quadrupolar) with distinct optical resonances known as Localized Surface Plasmon Resonances (LSPR). The oscillating electrons create concentrated electric fields at the metal surface, similar to a Faraday cage. With certain frequency approximations, the amplified Raman signals of a nearby molecule are proportional to the fourth power of the local electromagnetic field enhancement [7]. Geometric features of SERS substrates, like particle junctions or tips, can create extremely intense local fields, significantly increasing surface-enhanced Raman scattering [8]. These regions, known as “hot-spots,” are responsible for most of the observed SERS signals due to their high level of Raman amplification [9]. It is commonly accepted that, while the EME mechanism is more concerned with the substrate through its nature and geometry, the CE mechanism has more to deal with the molecule/substrate combination and their interactions [10].

The control and careful evaluation of the geometry (i.e., morphology and available hot-spots) and nature of the SERS substrate is therefore of fundamental importance once one would attempt SERS performance comparisons, for instance. An initial classification of SERS substrates may be their subdivision into liquid suspensions (e.g., colloids) or solid structures (e.g., self-assemblies of colloids into ordered layers and multilayers, crystals and supercrystals, chemically etched structures, etc.) [2]. The state-of-the-art in colloidal SERS substrates highlights high synthetic reproducibility, cost-effectiveness, and the tunability of sizes, shapes, and functionalization. Nonetheless, the control over the available hot-spots can be challenging. As an example, the simplest colloidal SERS substrates are nanospheres, where the difference in EME between isolated particles and aggregates is dramatic [2]. More sophisticated structures such as nanorods and nanostars can provide more stable SERS signals, due to the presence of intrinsic hot spots resulting from their anisotropic morphology [11–20]. On the other hand, the solid substrates made as thin films of aggregated/assembled colloids potentially offer more homogeneous three-dimensional hot-spot geometries, at least when averaged at the milli- or micron-scale [21–23]. The implementation of additive manufacturing techniques such as photolithography, inkjet printing, and chemical etching have shown great control over the size, shape, and density of hot spots [24]. The latest efforts in plasmonic substrates are represented by nano- and picocavities, capable of increasing local electric fields precisely at the atomic protrusions from the gold surface. These kinds of structures can increase the SERS signals of adsorbed molecules by factors up to 10^{12} [25].

Despite several colloidal, as well as solid, SERS substrates may be available on the market, within the SERS community it is common to produce your own substrates in-house, so that plenty of alternatives and variations over morphologies, production routes, and materials are present in specialized literature. A comprehensive overview in this sense is far out of the scope of this contribution. Nonetheless, there is something that most of them have in common, that is the efforts dedicated to the evaluation and comparison of the performance of a new SERS substrate with respect to the “competitors”. The SERS enhancement factor (EF) is nowadays the most popular

and important figure of merit for this scope [7, 26, 27]. It is defined as a general metric that quantifies how much more signal is expected to be observed under SERS conditions, compared to an equivalent “standard” Raman experiment [28]. In 2007, Pablo G. Etchegoin and Eric C. Le Ru published a milestone in the field, considered nowadays as the reference guide about SERS EF [7]. In their paper, several definitions and formalisms about EF are discussed, as well as some of the main experimental issues.

The most comprehensive definition of EF, indeed the one to which ultimately all others revert, is referred by them as SERS substrate EF (SSEF):

$$SSEF = \frac{I_{SERS}}{N_{SERS}} \bigg/ \frac{I_{Raman}}{N_{Raman}} \quad (1)$$

where I stands for the measured signal intensity (either SERS or by normal Raman), and N stands for the number of molecules responsible for the observed signals (again, in either SERS or normal Raman experiments). This kind of expression is ideal to match the average SERS EF $\langle EF \rangle$, relating to the overall SERS signals coming from a homogeneous molecular coverage [28]. Furthermore, it corresponds to the absolute EF of the scattering cross-section of the analyte, since it is determined by dividing the SERS intensity of one molecule of analyte by its normal Raman intensity [26]. However, in practice, it is very challenging to correctly estimate the values for N_{Raman} and N_{SERS} . In principle, it would require knowing, with extreme precision, the substrate morphology, molecular probe coverage (on nanostructured curved surfaces), and the excitation and collection volumes in solution or solid samples. Suitable techniques, whether existing for all the mentioned issues, may be tricky or not easily accessible. I_{Raman} and I_{SERS} need careful discussion as well, mostly related to the choice of proper molecular probes and measuring conditions [26]. Moreover, when considering resonant molecules like dyes, it can be difficult to measure I_{Raman} if fluorescence overwhelms the normal Raman signals, but is quenched for SERS experiments by the proximity of the metal [29].

Another practical definition of EF can be applied to analytes, which are first present in solution or gas phase, and then are deposited/adsorbed onto the SERS substrate (either solid or colloidal). This is known as the analytical enhancement factor (AEF) [7]:

$$AEF = \frac{I_{SERS}}{C_{SERS}} \bigg/ \frac{I_{Raman}}{C_{Raman}} \quad (2)$$

where C stands for the analyte concentration employed during the experiment preparation, either SERS or normal Raman. It works under the assumption that the SERS and Raman experiments are conducted under the same instrumental conditions (same optics and laser power) and that volume is constant through the two measures, as it is governed by the focal volume of the laser path. This makes the AEF an (experimentally) easier metric than SSEF, because it eliminates the need for estimating the number of molecules contributing to the signals. However,

some complications may arise from the transfer of the analyte from the solution to the substrate's surface. In fact, molecules with more affinity to the nanostructured surfaces, as well as more capable of replacing the already present molecules, can give higher SERS intensities [26, 28]. Indeed, adsorption equilibria are affected by the molecule concentration, which, if not considered, would result in another source of comparison error. As a whole, it makes AEF susceptible to underestimating the real enhancement, and it usually results in lower values when compared with SSEF [30]. Despite being subjected to severe limitations and approximations, as recently pointed out by Le Ru et al. [28], EF remains nowadays the gold standard methodology for establishing SERS performances [28]. A worth-mentioning alternative for determining the enhancement performance of SERS substrates was proposed by Yue et al., the SERS Performance Factor (SPF) [31]. This approach evaluates the sensitivity of a SERS calibration curve, namely the slope of I_{SERS} vs C_{SERS} of concentration-dependent Raman and SERS experiments. While this method demonstrates reliability and wide applicability across a variety of substrates and probes, it involves multiplications of samples and measures when compared to its closest analog, the AEF. In this article, a few examples among the most common and widely adopted SERS substrates are produced and characterized. Nanospheres of Ag and Au (AgNP and AuNP), and Au nanorods (AuNR) are used as colloids, while a thin film of AuNP obtained by spray-coating is used as a solid substrate. p-mercaptobenzoic acid (p-MBA), in water, is chosen as a probe molecule due to its commercial availability and wide adoption as SERS model probe [26]. It is out of resonance through the whole visible range and it provides strong covalent bonds to noble metals due to the thiol group [26]. These samples have been selected due to their familiarity to many established scientists in the SERS community, as well as a relatively easy starting point for newbies. A deep discussion is therefore presented about the main experimental concerns, and how to address rigorous and trustful SERS EF for any of the above-mentioned substrates. A solid substrate, with respect to a colloid, foresees a fundamentally different approach in addressing N_{Raman} and N_{SERS} , as well as how to set the spectrometer and how to collect significant data. All the instrumentations and methodologies herein considered are commonly available at any institute. An inspection of recent literature, focused on original papers dedicated to SERS and EF, clearly reflects a community not yet aligned with the protocols and precautions needed for a robust EF estimation. The discussion presented in the following addresses the basics behind a robust SERS EF estimation, through a step-by-step rigorous and detailed description of the experimental procedures, as a tutorial guideline especially dedicated to the new, welcome, scientists in the field.

2 | Experimental

All Raman and SERS experiments herein presented have been conducted using a Renishaw InVia Micro-Raman, equipped with 633 and 785 nm laser excitation. Grids (1200 and 1800 lines/mm) were employed depending on the excitation wavelength. p-MBA signals were established by the intensity at the maximum of the two main bands at 1080 and 1590 cm^{-1} , as well as the band integrals at $\pm 40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with respect to the maximum. All Raman and SERS spectra were background subtracted with the

built-in Renishaw's WiRE software, using a polynomial baseline (11th grade). These parameters remained the same for all the measurements herein presented, to ensure that no artifacts due to the application of different pre-processing methods arise when considering the final intensities and integrals of the p-MBA peaks and bands. This led to some negative spectral intensities in the lowest signal-to-noise ratio parts of some spectra, indeed of minor influence for the purposes of the study. Before any experiment, the μ -Raman instrument is calibrated thanks to an internal silicon reference. The intensity of its characteristic Raman peak at 520 cm^{-1} is used as reference for day-by-day reproducibility of the measured samples intensities, as well as reference along the Raman shift axis. Fluctuations within 5% were considered acceptable for reproducibility.

2.1 | Literature Survey

To assess the current status of how the SERS EF is calculated and presented, a literature review of recent EF-related papers has been conducted. Specifically, the survey is focused on the past two years (i.e., 2022 and 2023). To perform the search and limit the window of interest, the following query is programmed in the Scopus research engine (www.scopus.com), through the "Advanced document search" tool and setting the following query string:

(ABS (sers AND ef OR enhancement AND factor) AND KEY (sers AND ef OR enhancement AND factor)) AND PUBYEAR > 2021 AND PUBYEAR < 2024.

It results in a total of 56 documents, 47 of which are articles. Among these, seven were further rejected because non-accessible or not written in English. As a whole, the survey herein presented considered 40 original papers.

2.2 | Colloidal Substrates Synthesis

Gold and silver spherical nanoparticles (AuNPs and AgNPs) were synthesized via laser ablation synthesis in solution (LASiS), following a previously reported method [32, 33]. A pure gold or silver target was placed at the bottom of a glass cell in a 50 μM (for gold) or 20 μM (for silver) aqueous micromolar solution of NaCl. A Q-Smart 450 Nd:YAG laser (6 ns, 1064 nm) was focused on a 1 mm spot on the metallic target at a fluence of 1 J/cm^2 , with a repetition rate of 20 Hz. Ablation continued until the desired nanoparticle concentration was reached.

Gold nanorods (AuNRs) were prepared using a seed-growth approach. The seed solution was freshly prepared by quickly adding 300 μL of a 10 mM solution of NaBH_4 to a mixture of 4.7 mL of CTAB 100 mM and 25 μL of HAuCl_4 50 mM under vigorous stirring. The solution was stirred at 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ for an hour. For the growth, in a glass vial at 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ under moderate stirring were added in the following order: 10 mL of CTAB 100 mM, 100 μL of 50 mM HAuCl_4 , 40 μL of 10 mM AgNO_3 , 70 μL of 100 mM ascorbic acid and 10 μL of the seed. The mixture was left to react at 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min without stirring. The final product was purified by centrifugation and redispersed in a 1 mM CTAB aqueous solution.

All the particles were characterized using UV-vis-NIR spectroscopy and transmission electron microscopy (TEM, FEI Tecnai G2 12 operating at 100 kV and equipped with a TVIPS CCD camera).

2.3 | Fabrication and Characterization of Spray-Coated AuNP SERS Substrates

To produce the solid SERS substrates, the additive manufacturing technique of spray coating was used. In short, the spray coating process of a solution of gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), synthesized as in Section 2.2, on a microscope glass slide allows to obtain a plasmonic substrate possessing numerous hot-spots that allow the SERS effect to take place. In practice, the solution of gold nanoparticles is dispensed onto the glass surface, previously cleaned and sonicated in isopropyl alcohol, using a spray coater (airbrush). The distance between the spray coater nozzle and the glass surface is set to 20 cm. The pressure of the carrier nitrogen flow is set to 3.0 bar. The temperature of the plate on which the slide is placed is set to 150°C. A total of 20 mL of gold nanoparticle solution per sample is sprayed. The use of a steel template fixed to the glass slide allows to obtain a coarse patterning (a 2 × 10 mm rectangle) of the fabricated plasmonic film.

The thus obtained plasmonic films are characterized by acquiring SEM images and SNOM scans (see Figure 1). A Tria SPM station, from APE Research, was used for aperture-SNOM, shear force fork for topography and metalized optical fibers, 100 nm aperture, for SNOM at 660 nm. SEM images were acquired with a Zeiss Sigma HD microscope, equipped with a Schottky FEG source, one detector for backscattered electrons and two detectors for secondary electrons (InLens and Everhart Thornley). The microscope is coupled to an EDX detector (from Oxford Instruments, x-act PentaFET Precision) for X-rays microanalysis, working in energy dispersive mode.

2.4 | p-MBA Incubation on Spray-Coated AuNP SERS Substrates

A solution of 1.22 mM of p-MBA in 1.83 mM of NaOH in MilliQ water was prepared. The used concentration of p-MBA is well above the critical concentration (10^{-6} M) which guarantees the formation of self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) on top of roughened gold surfaces [34]. The SERS substrate is then incubated with this solution for a total of 3 h. The volume of p-MBA solution used is such as to guarantee total coverage of the surface to be analyzed by micro-Raman (i.e., 400 μ L). The incubation was protected against drying. It was carried out in a closed petri dish containing other wells filled with water, to saturate the atmosphere of the petri dish with vapor and thus avoiding the evaporation of the p-MBA solution. After 3 h, the MBA solution was gently removed from the surface, taking care not to dry it onto the gold surface. The Au surface was then rinsed twice with basic water (NaOH 0.61 mM), to remove all the left-over free p-MBA molecules. The residual washing water was drained (not dried) with the help of nitrogen flow. The SERS substrate was thus ready for surface-enhanced Raman scattering measurements.

2.5 | Normal Raman Experiments on p-MBA Tablet

A p-MBA powder tablet (height: 1 mm, diameter: 5 mm) was obtained by means of a hydraulic press. The disc was then used to perform a Raman mapping measurement along the *z*-axis (depth analysis) with steps of 2 μ m. The value of *z* = 0 μ m was assigned to the surface of the p-MBA tablet and the measure was spanned a few tens of microns above and below. The 1590 and the 1080 cm^{-1} p-MBA peaks were considered. The same conditions were also adopted for the SERS confocal measurements on top of the AuNP films (see the following section).

FIGURE 1 | Literature survey on articles published between 2022 and 2023, with “SERS” and “enhancement factor” both in the abstract and as keywords. A total of 40 documents were found with these criteria by the search engine. The logarithm scale in the plot (a) results in the superimposition of several entries.

2.6 | SERS Experiments on Spray-Coated AuNP SERS Substrates

After p-MBA incubation on top of the AuNP film surface, the SERS measurements were carried out. Extended 2D micro-Raman maps were acquired to obtain a high number of spectra, and thus to better represent the overall surface. Specifically, 400-points Raman maps were acquired for each laser line and laser power on the sample. The acquired maps span over a surface of about 0.16 mm^2 ($400 \times 400 \mu\text{m}$, steps of $20 \mu\text{m}$ both in x and y axes), using a $50\times$ NPlan Leica objective (0.75 NA), working in air. The same surface geometry was mapped for each measurement and the same location was used for 633 and 785 maps. For calculating the confocal volume during SERS experiments, a depth scan identical to those described in Section 2.5 was adopted. The focus plane is checked and selected through preliminary depth scans experiments along the z axis. The z position on top of the SERS substrates giving the highest p-MBA peak intensities and integrals is chosen as focal plane for conducting the 2D maps.

2.7 | Colloidal SERS Substrates: Functionalization with MBA, Controlled Aggregation, and SERS Characterization

For functionalization, $100 \mu\text{L}$ of 1 mM p-MBA in 2 mM NaOH in milliQ water were added to 1 mL of each colloidal solution. The mixtures were stirred for 3 h at room temperature. After functionalization, UV-Vis-NIR spectra and SERS spectra (using 633 and 785 nm excitation) were recorded without purification to avoid aggregation as much as possible. The mixtures were then centrifuged at 4000 RCF for 20 min to induce controlled aggregation and the precipitates were redispersed in 10^{-4} M aqueous solution of NaOH. UV-Vis-NIR spectra and SERS spectra were remeasured post-aggregation.

All the SERS spectra and the Raman spectra of a 100 mM reference solution of MBA were acquired using identical parameters: 1.5 mW laser power at 633 nm and 3 mW at 785 nm, same optics ($10\times$ NPlan Leica objective, 0.25 NA , through a quartz cuvette) and 20 s acquisition time. The acquisition was performed from the side of the cuvette, but with the care to place the laser focal volume right below the liquid surface to avoid attenuation from the solution.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Literature Survey

The state-of-the-art of the best and the most common approaches for the estimation of the SERS Enhancement Factor can be pictured by a survey of recent specialized literature. The SERS community is extremely rich, and more than 750 articles can be found by the Scopus engine when queried about “SERS” and “enhancement factor” within the abstract of any document published between 2022 and 2023. A detailed examination of such a huge number of documents is beyond the scope of this study, so the research was further limited to articles presenting the same selected keywords (refer to the experimental section

for details). The adopted criteria were intended to select the papers with a marked interest in determining the EFs, so that careful efforts would have been dedicated to that task. Forty different papers published between 2022 and 2023 were therefore selected [35–74]. To present the results of how EF was treated and calculated over the past two years, stringent criteria were posed to better discern the methodological approaches adopted around the SERS enhancement factor.

It is worth mentioning that the scope of this analysis is not to judge about “good” and “bad” science, assuming all studies were driven under genuine scientific curiosity, ethics, and fair peer-revision, but to effectively represent an inhomogeneous panorama over the evaluation of an unanimously recognized figure-of-merit in SERS.

The questions that drive the classification are the following.

1. Does the SERS substrate presented in the paper belong to colloids or solids?
2. Which model is used for calculating the EF?
3. For colloids only: is the EF evaluated in solution or on substrates in a deposited form?

This question aims to discern between analyzing the colloidal substrate in its native environment (i.e., in solution), or under different conditions (e.g., dropcasted, spincoated, etc. colloids).

4. For solids only: is the surface variability, and thus of the corresponding SERS signals, considered?

The purpose of this question is to check whether investigations have been made to assess the deviations in the SERS signals deriving from the variability/inhomogeneity of the surface, such as roughness for instance. Affirmative answers ascribe studies in which imaging, maps or multiple points taken at various positions on the substrate are provided and discussed.

5. Which probe molecule was used, and does it manifest fluorescence under the excitation chosen for the analysis?

While the purpose of the first part of the question is clear, the second part about fluorescence aims to distinguish whether the potential fluorescence of the probe molecules would have been a potential source of error [26].

6. Does the study evaluate I_{Raman} on the same Raman band used for I_{SERS} ?

It is known that the EF, on a fixed molecular probe, may vary in function of the specific band (vibrational mode) under consideration, for instance because of the so-called SERS surface selection rules [75, 76]. Affirmative answers ascribe studies in which Raman spectra, with a reasonable signal-to-noise ratio (roughly 3 times the standard deviation of the background noise) at the same I_{SERS} , are presented.

Figure 1 resumes the literature survey in a few pie charts. At first glance, a great variability is immediately revealed. The distributions in the enhancement factors (Figure 1a) reflect the variety of SERS substrates that will inherently have different

performances. It spreads over the huge window of 14 orders of magnitude almost independently through solid or colloidal substrate.

The first distinction in Figure 1b is about solid and colloidal substrates. The classification is made on the intended purpose of the substrate of any study, rather than the physical state of the substrate during the SERS measurement. Dropcasted suspensions were classified under colloids when the focus was on the SERS properties of the single nanostructures. Whereas, if drop-casting is just the fabrication method chosen for the preparation of the substrate, this was classified as solid.

Several techniques for thin film fabrications are based on inks of colloids [24]. On the counterpart, it was found that studies focused on colloids, indeed applied as colloidal SERS substrates, perform the EF estimation on a deposited form of the latter (i.e., dropcasted), Figure 1c. The aggregation state of a colloidal substrate may have a tremendous effect on the recovered SERS signal, as the amplification provided by the hot-spots may result dominant [14], even when aggregates represent only a small percentage of the substrate [13]. Despite this, less than 30% of the measurements for colloids were performed in their native environment, namely in solution (Figure 1c).

Solid substrates are found to be much more popular in the present ensemble. The same arguments adopted for colloids about the need to control, or at least take into account, aggregation, reflect on a solid substrate as well. Despite a colloid may be intended as a homogeneous dispersion (at least at the scale sampled by the Raman instrument), the same does not apply to a solid substrate. Morphological inhomogeneities are physiological to some extent and so, again, the spatially distributed SERS signals. Less than 40% of the studies about solid substrates considered this aspect (Figure 1d), and only 35% of the studies that did consider, presented more than 100 points analyzed.

Figure 1e resumes the distribution over the probe adopted for the measurements. A variety of different alternatives can be observed. Dye molecules are often used (>50%) as they provide very high Raman cross-sections due to resonant enhancement. There are however some issues with their usage [26]: their affinity to the substrate is usually not very high and mainly due to electrostatic interactions, chemical enhancement mechanisms might take part in the overall EF, and lastly, an important fluorescent background might be present in the Raman spectrum, making it difficult to accurately determine I_{Raman} . Despite this, the fluorescence could be avoided by a wise choice of the excitation wavelength, Figure 1f reveals that almost 50% of the studies used resonant conditions. p-Mercaptobenzoic acid (p-MBA) was also often used, as well as other non-dyes. This is an excellent non-resonant SERS probe with a very high affinity to gold surfaces and a good Raman cross-section. Other (non-dye) probes are often the same analytes for which the substrate was designed, and this is worth mentioning great practice when applicable. The distribution over the models adopted for the EF description is in Figure 1g. More than 50% used the most general SFEF, while AEF was used in 35% of the cases. The remaining section is about studies that did not explicitly mention how they calculated the EF. The last Figure 1h is about whether the Raman spectrum, see I_{Raman} , is present in the publication,

or not. A negative answer is assigned to situations in which the data is not provided, as well as the band supposed to be used for the I_{Raman} is far below an acceptable signal-to-noise, so one cannot really distinguish the Raman spectrum from the noise. It is worth noting that 40% of the cases fall into this category.

Overall, this survey reveals that the determination of the EF is still far from being standardized. This eventually complicates the comparison between different SERS substrates. Ultimately, this would be severely detrimental to the upgrade of SERS as a sensing technique suitable for commercialization. A detailed procedure for SERS EF estimation, in accordance with the state-of-the-art in the field, is schematically resumed in Figure 2 and discussed in detail in the following sections with the help of colloidal and solid substrates as case-studies.

3.2 | EF on Solid SERS Substrates

The solid substrate used in this study was produced by spray coating of an AuNP solution (Figure S1, Supporting Information) on a microscope glass slide (Figure S2, Supporting Information). Scanning Near Field Optical Microscopy (aperture-SNOM) was used to inspect the film (Figures 3a,b,c). It resulted in a thin film of about 200 nm thickness. The wide distribution of hot-spots is visible by SNOM analysis collected in reflection (Figure 3b) respect to transmission (Figure 3c). The scratch used to appreciate the thickness left a couple of little residues on the glass support. They are highlighted with a red circle in Figure 3a–c and, despite a clear contrast in transmission (meaning absorption of the laser), their contrast in reflection is negligible. The bright reflection that can be seen on the top of the thin film in Figure 3b is therefore assumed as due to the wide and compact presence of plasmonic couplings, i.e., hot-spots, indeed confirmed by electron microscopy (Figure 3d,e). The p-MBA was therefore added and the sample analyzed dry. The most comprehensive SFEF definition (Equation 1) was used, and a detailed dissertation about the geometry of the surface, the confocal (sampling) volume and the number of analyte molecules will follow.

3.2.1 | Determination of I_{SERS}

As already discussed, a single point of analysis cannot be representative of an entire surface, as the spatial variability is not negligible by definition, as it may be for solutions. The solid substrate was therefore mapped over $400 \times 400 \mu\text{m}^2$, by a grid spaced $20 \mu\text{m}$ (400 total points of analysis), using a $50\times$ magnification objective (0.75 NA). Both 633 and 785 nm excitation were used, and the obtained maps are resumed in Figure 4a, along with the distributions of SERS spectra. The two characteristic p-MBA aromatic ring vibrations, at around 1590 and 1080cm^{-1} assigned to ν_{8a} and ν_{12} [34], are considered for the scope of the calculation of I_{SERS} . The reason behind this choice is that both peaks are always present and unperturbed on both normal Raman and SERS [34]. For instance, these are not pH-sensitive [77]. There will therefore be a direct and unbiased comparison of the enhancement factor deriving from the interaction with the SERS substrate. Both the absolute intensities and the band integrals were considered in the following for comparison (Table S1, S2 and S3, Supporting Information).

SERS EF DETERMINATION: a practical guide

Colloidal SERS substrates

Solid SERS substrates

FIGURE 2 | A schematic resume for the procedures of the determination of SERS Enhancement Factor on colloidal, as well as solid substrates. Created with BioRender.com.

Figure 4b shows the averaged spectra for the whole Raman map, together with their standard deviation.

3.2.2 | Determination of I_{Raman}

The measurements for the I_{Raman} were performed on p-MBA crystals in the form of a tablet. The same laser wavelengths, optics, and powers were used in the I_{SERS} measurements. In this case, the x - y variability is neglected as the sample is a pure substance, but not the variability along z . Further discussion about N_{Raman} would need to approximate the whole confocal volume

of sampling coming from inside the p-MBA tablet. In practice, it is assumed that the Raman spectrum (Figure S3a, Supporting Information) with the highest absolute intensities for the two diagnostic peaks is considered to be ascribed to the abovementioned condition (Figure S3b, Supporting Information).

3.2.3 | Determination of N_{SERS}

The value of interest to determine the number of p-MBA molecules covalently linked to the Au substrate is represented by the effective sample surface under the laser spot. First, it is

FIGURE 3 | (a) Topography of the solid SERS substrate, along with three height profiles. The scratch was used to effectively determine the film's thickness. The small AuNP residues, highlighted in the dashed red circle, possess a non-negligible height. (b) a-SNOM reflection measurement of the solid SERS substrate. The small AuNP residues (in the dashed red circle) are barely visible. (c) a-SNOM transmission measurement of the solid SERS substrate. The small AuNP residues are clearly detectable. (d) and (e) SEM micrographs of the solid SERS substrate at different degrees of magnification.

necessary to determine the geometrical area A_{geom} (μm^2) irradiated by the laser spot. A perfect circular laser spot is assumed, so this quantity is defined as follows [78]:

$$A_{geom} (\mu\text{m}^2) = \pi \cdot w_0^2 \quad (3)$$

where w_0 is the probe volume radius, which can be written as:

$$w_0 = \sqrt{\frac{z_0 \cdot \lambda}{\pi \cdot n}} \quad (4)$$

where z_0 is the half-height of the probe volume, λ is the excitation wavelength in μm , and n is the refractive index of the analyte molecule. z_0 can be derived from a Raman mapping scan along the z axis (depth scan, Figure S4, Supporting Information) on top of the substrate incubated with the p-MBA. This experiment, similar in concept to the one conducted on top of the p-MBA tablet, allows the user to find the trend of the intensity of the diagnostic SERS peaks of MBA as a function of z , characterized by the typical Gaussian shape (Figure S5, Supporting Information). Subsequently, z_0 can be extrapolated by the Gaussian's full width at half maximum (FWHM) [78]:

$$z_0 (\mu\text{m}) = \frac{FWHM(\mu\text{m})}{2} \quad (5)$$

Overall, Equations 3, 4, and 5 can be united and simplified as:

$$A_{geom} (\mu\text{m}^2) = \frac{FWHM(\mu\text{m}) \cdot \lambda(\mu\text{m})}{2n} \quad (6)$$

If dealing with a flat and homogeneous SERS substrate, knowing the steric hindrance of the MBA, one could quickly come to the number of MBA molecules within the area irradiated by the laser spot. However, the structure of the SERS substrates is commonly far from been flat. One may say that it will not work at all if perfectly flat, indeed. It is therefore necessary to consider the roughness of the substrate to find out the real, effective, area under the laser spot (referred as "ironed area", or A_{ironed}). A topography measurement (typically by an SPM station like AFM, SNOM and STM) is therefore needed to estimate the substrate's roughness, and so the "ironed" surface. The roughness R is thus given by:

$$R = \frac{SPM \text{ Scanned area } (\mu\text{m}^2)}{SPM \text{ Ironed surface } (\mu\text{m}^2)} \quad (7)$$

which for rough substrates is always less than 1. For the solid substrates of interest, the topography obtained by a-SNOM measurements, over $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$, resulted to an R equal to 0.985. Since the a-SNOM scan was done on the same location used for the Raman mapping (see I_{SERS}), R can be also used for obtaining the A_{ironed} :

$$A_{ironed} (\mu\text{m}^2) = \frac{A_{geom} (\mu\text{m}^2)}{R} \quad (8)$$

Finally, N_{SERS} is given by the number of p-MBA molecules, assuming a packed monolayer, on top of the surface given by A_{ironed} . Knowing the steric surface hindrance of a single MBA molecule (0.38 nm^2) [79], one could derive the following equation:

FIGURE 4 | (a) 2D SERS maps of the same analysed area of the solid SERS substrate, investigated with different excitation wavelengths and two selected peaks. The distributions of the intensities of the SERS spectra are reported. (b) Averaged spectra of p-MBA on top of the solid SERS substrate, for each excitation wavelength. The standard deviation at each Raman shift is displayed in red.

$$N_{SERS} = \frac{A_{ironed} (nm^2)}{steric\ surface\ hindrance_{MBA} (nm^2)} \quad (9)$$

This calculation represents an order-of-magnitude estimation, as p-MBA is unlikely to exhibit a hexagonal close-packed arrangement, particularly on a rough surface [80, 81]. Nevertheless, it serves as a conservative approximation, as assuming an N_{SERS} value greater than the actual value may lead to an underestimation of the final EF rather than an overestimation. It is important to repeat the SERS depth experiment for each experimental acquisition condition (objective and laser wavelength/power), since the area under the laser spot, as well as the A_{ironed} , can vary significantly (Table S1, Supporting Information).

3.2.4 | Determination of N_{Raman}

The experiment that is performed for finding N_{Raman} , as previously mentioned, is given by the assumption that all the

I_{Raman} comes from inside sampling volume of the laser within the p-MBA tablet.

The sampling volume, or confocal volume, is defined by [78]:

$$V_{confocal} (\mu m^3) = \pi^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot w_0^2 \cdot z_0 \quad (10)$$

where, as before, w_0^2 and z_0 are the probe volume radius and its half-height, respectively. Given Equations 4 and 5, one could rewrite Equation 10 as follows:

$$V_{confocal} (\mu m^3) = \frac{\pi^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot FWHM^2 \cdot \lambda}{4\pi n} \quad (11)$$

where the FWHM is again derived from the Gaussian fit of the I_{Raman} intensities and integrals (Table S1, Supporting Information) as function of the z values of the Raman depth measurements, λ is the excitation wavelength in μm , and n is the refractive index of MBA ($n=1.552$) [82]. Knowing

the density of MBA ($\rho_{\text{MBA}} = 1.5 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and its molar weight ($\text{MW}_{\text{MBA}} = 154.19 \text{ g/mol}$), one could easily derive N_{Raman} [83]:

$$N_{\text{Raman}} = \frac{\rho_{\text{MBA}} \cdot V_{\text{confocal}}}{\text{MW}_{\text{MBA}}} \cdot N_A \quad (12)$$

where N_A is Avogadro's number.

3.2.5 | EF Results

The definition illustrated in Equation 1 was adopted and the resulting EFs for the solid plasmonic substrate are in the range of 10^4 – 10^7 (Figure S10, Supporting Information), depending on the acquisition conditions, as reported on Table S3 (Supporting Information) and Figure 4. These enhancement magnitudes fall perfectly in what Le Ru et al. describe as average EFs of most SERS substrates [28, 84, 85].

Several local and singular spots within the investigated area show enhancements much higher than average (roughly one order of magnitude) (Figure 4). This could reasonably indicate much more effective hot-spots in those areas [28]. Indeed, this underlies the importance for accounting the spatial distribution of the EF once facing with solid substrates. The herein proposed method for evaluating the EF on solid substrates is relatively simple, does not require extremely specialized instruments, but at least one main limitation is certainly recognized. SPM measures, at the best of the possible performance, can only achieve surface topography at the lateral resolution provided by the tip curvature, and it is intrinsically unable to describe the film surface in detail. In fact, the pores highlighted by the SEM images (Figure 3d,e) cannot be resolved by this technique. To obtain the most descriptive result possible, it would be appropriate to use techniques that also allow to establish the micro- and nanoporosity present inside and (possibly) underneath the film. For example, gas permeability measurements [86, 87] on a porous solid substrate can ensure a more truthful description of its roughness R , and ultimately a more representative EF of the SERS substrate. As another example, electrochemical desorption represents a robust technique for quantifying the surface coverage of a molecule adsorbed on a gold film, relying on the precise relationship between the current measured under a properly applied potential, and the number of molecules initially present on the surface [88].

3.3 | EF Determination of Colloidal Suspensions

Three different colloidal suspensions were taken as examples of colloidal SERS substrates: gold spherical nanoparticles (AuNPs), silver spherical nanoparticles (AgNPs) and gold nanorods (AuNRs), Figure 5. The nanostructures were functionalized with p-MBA and SERS spectra were acquired in their native environment, i.e., liquid. The colloidal suspensions were then centrifuged to cause aggregation and SERS spectra were acquired again to estimate the effect of the aggregation. The SERS intensities were compared with the spectra of a reference concentrated solution of p-MBA.

The determination of EF is somehow easier with colloidal suspensions. If colloids are stable, they are homogeneous samples, eliminating the issue of averaging over a large number of spectra (see Raman mapping). The formula adopted for the determination of the EF is the one for the analytical enhancement factor (AEF, Equation 2). This model can be derived by the SSEF (Equation 13), and it results particularly effective from the applicability point of view, whether basic good practices are adopted.

$$\text{SEEF} = \frac{I_{\text{SERS}}}{N_{\text{SERS}}} \bigg/ \frac{I_{\text{Raman}}}{N_{\text{Raman}}} = \frac{I_{\text{SERS}}}{(C_{\text{SERS}} \times V \times N_A)} \bigg/ \frac{I_{\text{Raman}}}{(C_{\text{Raman}} \times V \times N_A)} \quad (13)$$

The fundamental concern is about the confocal volumes of the laser path. In principle, one should determine the volume sampled by the laser (that ultimately gives the N_{Raman} and N_{SERS}) for any measure. Nonetheless, it can be simplified since identical parameters (same objective, laser power, collection set-up, sample container, and so on) were adopted for both SERS and Raman measurements, giving an unambiguous experimental advantage.

3.3.1 | Determination of C_{Raman} and C_{SERS}

C_{Raman} is simply the concentration of p-MBA, in basic environment to provide stable solubility in water. It must be recalled that thiols may dimerize under basic conditions, so that the sample must be prepared and used fresh. In any case, as already discussed, the p-MBA bands selected for the investigation are not directly related to the thiols. A concentration of 0.1 M was used to provide reasonable Raman signals (Figure S6, Supporting Information).

C_{SERS} was calculated starting from the p-MBA concentration used for the functionalization (10^{-4} M), and the concentration of nanoparticles. The first must be chosen in order to provide enough molecules for saturating the nanostructures surface, while minimizing the possible contribution of Raman signals from not-bounded p-MBA. An approximation was eventually done by considering only the first monolayer of p-MBA, on the surface of the nanostructures, to be involved in SERS enhancement. This is supported by the strong distance dependence of the enhanced local EM field from the surface that decays as $1/d^3$ when moving away from the surface [10]. AuNPs concentration was calculated by fitting the UV-Vis-NIR spectra of the non-aggregated particles with a simulated spectra obtained by BEM simulations following a previously published method [13]. AgNPs concentration was calculated based on the absorbance on the plasmonic peak, the extinction cross-section was once again calculated with BEM simulations (Figure S7, Supporting Information). AuNRs particle concentration was calculated starting from the concentration in atomic gold, that can be obtained from the absorbance at 450 nm, relative to the interband transitions of d-band electrons [89]. The size of the rods was obtained from TEM inspection and the volume and surface of the rod were calculated by approximating the shape to the sum of a cylinder and two semi spheres.

FIGURE 5 | UV-Vis-NIR spectra of the colloidal solutions before and after aggregation and TEM images of the nanoparticles; SERS spectra of the aggregated colloids acquired at 633 and 785 nm.

The concentration of nanoparticles in the aggregated solution were evaluated starting from the non-aggregated concentration and by comparing the absorbances relative to the interband transitions of d-band electrons (450 nm for gold and 250 nm for silver). This consideration accounts for the possible losses during the centrifugation and redispersion step. All the concentrations were multiplied for the average surface area of the single nanoparticles (whose size can be obtained by TEM images, Figure 5 and Figure S8, Supporting Information) and divided by the surface hindrance of p-MBA (0.38 nm^2) to finally obtain the $C_{\text{SERS-MBA}}$.

3.3.2 | EF Results

All the Raman and SERS spectra, acquired at two different excitation wavelengths are reported in Figure 5 and Figure S6 (Supporting Information), and the obtained EF are listed in Table S1 (Supporting Information) and Figure S11. Colloidal

suspensions of nanoparticles represent perhaps the simplest example of a SERS substrate: they are easy to synthesize, and their production can be easily scaled up. They exhibit, however, inherent instability over time due to their metastable nature: they can undergo degradation during storage and use, through aggregation, precipitation and even dissolution based on the environment and their surface functionalization. Aggregation can be advantageous in SERS, as it creates hot-spots between nanoparticles. Controlled aggregation must be carefully monitored to avoid excessive clustering, which can diminish SERS performance and/or lead to precipitation. UV-vis-NIR spectroscopy can be a simple but effective technique to monitor changes in colloidal systems. Aggregation results in a broadening and red-shifting of the plasmonic bands, confirming the formation of nanoparticle clusters [13]. The effect of aggregation on SERS performances is particularly evident with spheres (Au and AgNP): they initially showed no significant aggregation, and thus very low or non-detectable SERS signal were present under these conditions. This is consistent with

the absence of hot-spots. Upon controlled aggregation post-centrifugation, the formed hot-spots significantly enhanced the SERS signal, as evidenced by the emergence of characteristic peaks in the p-MBA spectra. In contrast, AgNPs exhibited some degree of aggregation before functionalization, allowing for detectable SERS signals prior to centrifugation (Figure S9, Supporting Information). After centrifugation, the aggregation intensified, causing an increase in the SERS enhancement factor (EF) as well. Finally, AuNRs, due to their anisotropic shape, inherently possess plasmonic hot-spots at their tips. This geometry enables substantial SERS activity even prior to aggregation (Figure S9, Supporting Information). After centrifugation, a slight aggregation was observed (Figure S10, Supporting Information) and additional hot-spots were created, leading to a further boost in EF. Once again, the resulting EFs of these substrates fall in the range between 10^4 and 10^6 , well in line with the average reported values (Figure S11, Supporting Information) [28]. The variability in EF estimation, in terms of wavelength and “intensity” or “integral” of signals, is greater for solid SERS substrates compared to colloidal ones. At first, the resonance condition of the laser with the plasmonic band of the substrate strongly influences the strength of the Raman enhancement. All the colloidal substrates have similar extinctions for both the lasers used along the same sample. It is reflected in the minimal variability passing from 633 to 785 nm excitation when the colloidal solutions are measured, as opposed to the more pronounced variation for the solid substrate (Figure S12, Supporting Information). The variability observed in the SERS measurements using band intensities, or band integrals, can be assigned to the degree of freedom of the molecules/nanoparticles. Uneven hot-spot distributions and different molecule-substrate interactions and orientations is known to provide broader SERS bands due to the so-called inhomogeneous broadening [90]. Thermal broadening is also prominent in solid SERS substrates, where heat generated by plasmonic excitation is less efficiently dissipated [91], unlike in liquid substrates where water attenuates the effect. Moreover, the p-MBA powder was used for the Raman reference in the EF calculation of the solid SERS sample. Its crystalline nature provides sharper peaks, with respect of the p-MBA solution used for the Raman in the EF for colloidal SERS substrates. Both the inhomogeneous and thermal broadening, and the crystalline nature of the sample used for the Raman reference, contributed to making EF of solid samples recursively higher when “integrals” are used. It is finally worth mentioning that unlike in the near-field, far-field measurements accounting for optical attenuations, distortions, interferences and so on essentially averaged in the resulting measurable signal. EF estimated on the base of far-field measurements are therefore potentially affected by these effects. For example, it is reported that a 633 nm laser can be attenuated by ~25% passing through 20 nm Au nanoplates [92]. It should however be noted that the EFs in SERS experiments, as herein considered and described, inherently account for these variables, and comparisons are still valid once all experimental parameters and samples used for normal Raman are kept consistent. In simple terms, a thin film, as well as a colloidal solution, able to get in resonance with the excitation laser without losing much of its energy in ohmic losses will result in higher enhancement factors even just for this fact, as known when silver is used in respect of gold (taking possibly constant all other variables), for instance.

4 | Conclusions

This paper introduces a standardized methodology for accurately determining the SERS Enhancement Factor (EF) across both colloidal and solid substrates. The procedure, based on the use of the non-resonant probe p-MBA, has demonstrated its reliability in assessing the performance of commonly used gold and silver nanoparticle-based substrates. For solid substrates, statistical averaging and careful consideration of substrate roughness allow for precise EF calculations, while for colloidal systems, the importance of characterization of the suspensions over time is highlighted since aggregation can strongly affect SERS signal enhancement through hotspot formation. The measured EFs, ranging between 10^4 and 10^7 , align with reported literature values, confirming the robustness of the approach. This method provides a valuable framework, and it can represent a useful guide for reproducible and quantitative evaluation of SERS performance, facilitating better comparison and optimization of SERS substrates in practical applications.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

1. M. Fleischmann, P. J. Hendra, and A. J. McQuillan, “Raman Spectra of Pyridine Adsorbed at a Silver Electrode,” *Chemical Physics Letters* 26, no. 2 (1974): 163–166, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614\(74\)85388-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614(74)85388-1).
2. J. Langer, D. Jimenez de Aberasturi, J. Aizpurua, et al., “Present and Future of Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering,” *ACS Nano* 14, no. 1 (2020): 28–117, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.9b04224>.
3. E. Cara, L. Mandrile, A. Sacco, et al., “Towards a Traceable Enhancement Factor in Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy,” *Journal of Materials Chemistry C* 8, no. 46 (2020): 16513–16519, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0TC04364H>.
4. A. Del Tedesco, V. Piotto, G. Sponchia, et al., “Zirconia-Based Magnetoplasmonic Nanocomposites: A New Nanotool for Magnetic-Guided Separations with SERS Identification,” *ACS Applied Nano Materials* 3, no. 2 (2020): 1232–1241, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnm.9b01982>.
5. G. Sciuotto, S. Prati, I. Bonacini, L. Litti, M. Meneghetti, and R. Mazzeo, “A New Integrated TLC/MU-ATR/SERS Advanced Approach for the Identification of Trace Amounts of Dyes in Mixtures,” *Analytica Chimica Acta* 991 (2017): 104–112, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2017.08.020>.
6. S.-Y. Ding, E.-M. You, Z.-Q. Tian, and M. Moskovits, “Electromagnetic Theories of Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy,” *Chemical*

- Society Reviews* 46, no. 13 (2017): 4042–4076, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CS00238F>.
7. E. C. Le Ru, E. Blackie, M. Meyer, and P. G. Etchegoin, “Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering Enhancement Factors: A Comprehensive Study,” *Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 111, no. 37 (2007): 13794–13803, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp0687908>.
8. D. Radziuk and H. Moehwald, “Prospects for Plasmonic Hot Spots in Single Molecule SERS towards the Chemical Imaging of Live Cells,” *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* 17, no. 33 (2015): 21072–21093, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4CP04946B>.
9. R. C. Maher, “SERS Hot Spots,” in *Raman Spectroscopy for Nanomaterials Characterization*, ed. C. S. S. R. Kumar (Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012): 215–260, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-20620-7_10.
10. E. L. Ru and P. Etchegoin, *Principles of Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy: And Related Plasmonic Effects* (Great Britain: Elsevier, 2008).
11. N. Pazos-Pérez, S. Barbosa, L. Rodríguez-Lorenzo, et al., “Growth of Sharp Tips on Gold Nanowires Leads to Increased Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering Activity,” *Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters* 1, no. 1 (2010): 24–27, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jz900004h>.
12. E. Nalbant Esenturk and A. R. Hight Walker, “Surface-enhanced Raman Scattering Spectroscopy via Gold Nanostars,” *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy* 40, no. 1 (2009): 86–91, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrs.2084>.
13. L. Litti and M. Meneghetti, “Predictions on the SERS Enhancement Factor of Gold Nanosphere Aggregate Samples,” *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* 21, no. 28 (2019): 15515–15522, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9CP02015B>.
14. D. M. Solís, J. M. Taboada, F. Obelleiro, L. M. Liz-Marzán, and F. J. García De Abajo, “Optimization of Nanoparticle-Based SERS Substrates through Large-Scale Realistic Simulations,” *ACS Photonics* 4, no. 2 (2017): 329–337, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsphotonics.6b00786>.
15. J. Reguera, J. Langer, D. Jiménez De Aberasturi, and L. M. Liz-Marzán, “Anisotropic Metal Nanoparticles for Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering,” *Chemical Society Reviews* 46, no. 13 (2017): 3866–3885, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CS00158D>.
16. L. B. Berganza, L. Litti, M. Meneghetti, S. Lanceros-Méndez, and J. Reguera, “Enhancement of Magnetic Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering Detection by Tailoring Fe₃O₄@Au Nanorod Shell Thickness and Its Application in the On-Site Detection of Antibiotics in Water,” *ACS Omega* 7, no. 49 (2022): 45493–45503, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.2c06099>.
17. L. Litti, A. Colusso, M. Pinto, et al., “SERRS Multiplexing with Multivalent Nanostructures for the Identification and Enumeration of Epithelial and Mesenchymal Cells,” *Scientific Reports* 10, no. 1 (2020): 15805, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-72911-w>.
18. E. Lenzi, L. Litti, D. Jimenez De Aberasturi, M. Henriksen-Lacey, and L. M. Liz-Marzán, “SERSTEM: An App for the Statistical Analysis of Correlative SERS and TEM Imaging and Evaluation of SERS Tags Performance,” *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy* 52, no. 2 (2021): 355–365, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrs.6043>.
19. F. Cardoni, M. Meneghetti, and L. Litti, “3D SERS and Raman Imaging of Protective Microcapsules Containing Bio-active Terpenoids,” *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy* 55, no. 1 (2024): 6–14, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrs.6613>.
20. A. Mercedi, G. Gentili, V. Poli, et al., “Selective Labeling of Small Microplastics with SERS-Tags Based on Gold Nanostars: Method Optimization Using Polystyrene Beads and Application in Environmental Samples,” *ACS Omega* 9, no. 39 (2024): 40821–40831, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.4c05693>.
21. C. Farcau and S. Astilean, “Mapping the SERS Efficiency and Hot-Spots Localization on Gold Film over Nanospheres Substrates,” *Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 114, no. 27 (2010): 11717–11722, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp100861w>.
22. S. Park, J. Lee, and H. Ko, “Transparent and Flexible Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) Sensors Based on Gold Nanostar Arrays Embedded in Silicon Rubber Film,” *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 9, no. 50 (2017): 44088–44095, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.7b14022>.
23. M. Condorelli, L. Litti, M. Pulvirenti, V. Scardaci, M. Meneghetti, and G. Compagnini, “Silver Nanoplates Paved PMMA Cuvettes as a Cheap and Re-Usable Plasmonic Sensing Device,” *Applied Surface Science* 566 (2021): 150701, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2021.150701>.
24. S. Ricci, M. Buonomo, S. Casalini, S. Bonacchi, M. Meneghetti, and L. Litti, “High Performance Multi-Purpose Nanostructured Thin Films by Inkjet Printing: Au Micro-Electrodes and SERS Substrates,” *Nanoscale Advances* 5, no. 7 (2023): 1970–1977, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2NA00917J>.
25. J. J. Baumberg, “Picocavities: A Primer,” *Nano Letters* 22, no. 14 (2022): 5859–5865, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.2c01695>.
26. S. E. J. Bell, G. Charron, E. Cortés, et al., “Towards Reliable and Quantitative Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS): From Key Parameters to Good Analytical Practice,” *Angewandte Chemie, International Edition* 59, no. 14 (2020): 5454–5462, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201908154>.
27. R. Goodacre, D. Graham, and K. Faulds, “Recent Developments in Quantitative SERS: Moving towards Absolute Quantification,” *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry* 102 (2018): 359–368, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2018.03.005>.
28. E. C. Le Ru and B. Auguie, “Enhancement Factors: A Central Concept during 50 Years of Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy,” *ACS Nano* 18, no. 14 (2024): 9773–9783, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.4c01474>.
29. B. Auguie, A. Reigie, E. C. Le Ru, and P. G. Etchegoin, “Tiny Peaks vs Mega Backgrounds: A General Spectroscopic Method with Applications in Resonant Raman Scattering and Atmospheric Absorptions,” *Analytical Chemistry* 84, no. 18 (2012): 7938–7945, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac301696p>.
30. N. G. Khlebtsov and E. C. Le Ru, “Analytical Solutions for the Surface- and Orientation-averaged SERS Enhancement Factor of Small Plasmonic Particles,” *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy* 52, no. 2 (2021): 285–295, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrs.5980>.
31. X. Yue, S. Yan, T. Gao, et al., “SERS Performance Factor: A Convenient Parameter for the Enhancement Evaluation of SERS Substrates,” *Analytical Chemistry* 96 (2024): acs.analchem.4c02624, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.4c02624>.
32. V. Piotto, L. Litti, and M. Meneghetti, “Synthesis and Shape Manipulation of Anisotropic Gold Nanoparticles by Laser Ablation in Solution,” *Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 124, no. 8 (2020): 4820–4826, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b10793>.
33. E. Fazio, B. Gökce, A. De Giacomo, et al., “Nanoparticles Engineering by Pulsed Laser Ablation in Liquids: Concepts and Applications,” *Nanomaterials* 10, no. 11 (2020): 2317, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10112317>.
34. A. Michota and J. Bukowska, “Surface-enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) of 4-mercaptobenzoic Acid on Silver and Gold Substrates,” *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy* 34, no. 1 (2003): 21–25, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrs.928>.
35. L. Sherpa, N. Arun, S. V. S. Nageswara Rao, et al., “200 MeV Ag Ion Irradiation Mediated Green Synthesis and Self Assembly of Silver Nanoparticles into Dendrites for Enhanced SERS Applications,” *Radiation Physics and Chemistry* 193 (2022): 109966, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radphyschem.2022.109966>.
36. M. K. Francis, B. K. Sahu, P. B. Bhargav, et al., “Ag Nanowires Based SERS Substrates with Very High Enhancement Factor,” *Physica*

- E: *Low-dimensional Systems and Nanostructures* 137 (2022): 115080, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physe.2021.115080>.
37. X. Bian, J. Xu, Y. Pu, J. Yang, K. Chiu, and S. Jiang, "Ag-Coated Cotton Fabric as Ultrasensitive and Flexible SERS Substrate," *Journal of Industrial Textiles* 51, no. 1_suppl (2022): 712S–727S, <https://doi.org/10.1177/152808372111027781>.
38. M. Tiwari, A. Singh, S. Dureja, S. Basu, and S. K. Pattanayek, "Au Nanoparticles Decorated ZnO/ZnFe₂O₄ Composite SERS-Active Substrate for Melamine Detection," *Talanta* 236 (2022): 122819, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2021.122819>.
39. H. Yuan, S. Yu, M. Kim, et al., "Dopamine-Mediated Self-Assembled Anisotropic Au Nanoworms Conjugated with MoS₂ Nanosheets for SERS-Based Sensing," *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 371 (2022): 132453, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2022.132453>.
40. M. Haribabu, B. Dipanjan, M. S. Bharati, et al., "Exciton-Mediated Surface-Enhanced Raman Studies of Aluminum Doped Platinum Nano Colloids," *Optical Materials* 133 (2022): 113013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2022.113013>.
41. S. Biswas, Y. D. Devi, D. Sarma, N. D. Namsa, and P. Nath, "Gold Nanoparticle Decorated Blu-Ray Digital Versatile Disc as a Highly Reproducible Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering Substrate for Detection and Analysis of Rotavirus RNA in Laboratory Environment," *Journal of Biophotonics* 15, no. 11 (2022): e202200138, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbio.202200138>.
42. N. Ha Anh, M. Quan Doan, N. Xuan Dinh, T. Quang Huy, D. Quang Tri, and A.-T. Le, "Gold Nanoparticles-Based SERS Nanosensor for Thiram and Chloramphenicol Monitoring in Food Samples: Insight into Effects of Analyte Molecular Structure on Their Sensing Performance and Signal Enhancement," *Applied Surface Science* 584 (2022): 152555, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2022.152555>.
43. H.-Y. Wu, H.-C. Lin, G.-Y. Hung, et al., "High Sensitivity SERS Substrate of a Few Nanometers Single-Layer Silver Thickness Fabricated by DC Magnetron Sputtering Technology," *Nanomaterials* 12, no. 16 (2022): 2742, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12162742>.
44. I. Aleknavičienė, E. Pabrėža, M. Talaikis, M. Jankunec, and G. Račiukaitis, "Low-Cost SERS Substrate Featuring Laser-Ablated Amorphous Nanostructure," *Applied Surface Science* 571 (2022): 151248, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2021.151248>.
45. R. K. Saini, A. K. Sharma, A. Agarwal, and R. Prajesh, "Near Field FEM Simulations of Plasmonic Gold Nanoparticle Based SERS Substrate with Experimental Validation," *Materials Chemistry and Physics* 287 (2022): 126288, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2022.126288>.
46. N. S. Singh, F. Mayanglambam, H. B. Nemade, and P. K. Giri, "Plasma-Treated Graphene Surfaces for Trace Dye Detection Using Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy," *ACS Applied Nano Materials* 5, no. 5 (2022): 6352–6364, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.2c00445>.
47. F. J. Moaen and H. R. Humud, "Raman Scattering Enhancement by Silver Nanostructures Prepared by Electrical Exploding Wire Technique," *Iraqi Journal of Science* 63, no. 5 (2022): 2017–2024, <https://doi.org/10.24996/ij.s.2022.63.5.17>.
48. W. Ahmed, İ. M. Öztürk, R. M. F. Iftikhar, and A. Bek, "Seedless, Size and Shape Controlled Synthesis of Gold Mesoscopic Particles and Their Excellent SERS Applications," *Materials Chemistry and Physics* 278 (2022): 125589, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2021.125589>.
49. H. Wu, S. Chen, Y. Wang, et al., "Spiny Gold Nanoparticles Colloids as Substrate for Sensing of Methyl Parathion Based on Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering," *Materials Letters* 313 (2022): 131687, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2022.131687>.
50. F. C. Marques, G. C. Azevedo, C. A. Senna, et al., "Structural Characterization and Plasmonic Properties of Manganese Oxide-Coated Gold Nanorods," *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy* 272 (2022): 120988, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2022.120988>.
51. L. Lan, H. Yao, G. Li, X. Fan, M. Li, and T. Qiu, "Structural Engineering of Transition-Metal Nitrides for Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering Chips," *Nano Research* 15, no. 4 (2022): 3794–3803, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-021-3904-z>.
52. N. Singh, A. M. Shrivastav, N. Vashistha, and I. Abdulhalim, "3D Plasmonic Hot Spots Network via Gold Decorated Deep Micro-Porous Silicon Exhibiting Ultrahigh-SERS Enhancement with Application to Explosives Detection," *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 374 (2023): 132813, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2022.132813>.
53. A. Brancato, M. Condorelli, L. Salemi, et al., "Ag Nanoflowers as Single-Particle, Multi-Wavelength SERS Active Platforms," *Surfaces and Interfaces* 40 (2023): 103157, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2023.103157>.
54. L. Jiang, J. Zhang, H. Li, et al., "Band Gap Tuning of Sn_{1-x}Ce_xO₂ Nanoflower for Improved SERS Activity of Bioassay," *Chemical Engineering Journal* 461 (2023): 142102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.142102>.
55. P. Varasteanu, A. M. Bujor, C. Pachiu, et al., "Close-Packed Small Nanocubes Assemblies as Efficient SERS Substrates," *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1294 (2023): 136441, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2023.136441>.
56. M. V. Limaye, M. Pramanik, A. Moza, and S. B. Singh, "Composite of Two-Dimensional Vanadium Carbide MXene and Cellulose Nanocrystals for Detection of Analytes," *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy* 54, no. 4 (2023): 363–370, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrs.6497>.
57. H. Le Thi Minh, L. Tran Thi, H. Kim Nhat, et al., "Conductivity Support of AZO in Enhancements of SERS Ag/AZO Substrate to Detect Ketoprofen," *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics* 34, no. 4 (2023): 283, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-022-09704-6>.
58. Y. Zhu, J. Tian, M. Li, et al., "Construction of Graphene@Ag-MLF Composite Structure SERS Platform and Its Differentiating Performance for Different Foodborne Bacterial Spores," *Microchimica Acta* 190, no. 12 (2023): 472, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-023-06031-3>.
59. J. Dong, Y. Ren, K. Zhao, et al., "Electric Field-Induced Assembly of Au-Ag Alloy Nanoparticles into Nano-Reticulation for Ultrasensitive SERS," *Optics Express* 31, no. 13 (2023): 21225–21238, <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.493374>.
60. Y. Wu, S. Tang, R. Li, Y. Wang, and C. Wu, "From 'Tanghulu' to 'Sausage': Gold Nanosheets-Decorated TiO₂ Nanocolumns/Carbon Fiber as SERS Substrate," *Journal of Materials Science* 58, no. 31 (2023): 12624–12634, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-023-08816-6>.
61. N. Li, X. Huang, H. Dong, et al., "Gold-Coated Nanoripples Produced by UV-Femtosecond Lasers for Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy," *Applied Surface Science* 636 (2023): 157794, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2023.157794>.
62. L. T. M. Huyen, N. T. Phuc, H. T. D. Khanh, and L. V. T. Hung, "Increasing Charge Transfer of SERS by the Combination of Amorphous Al₂O₃-Al Thin Film and ZnO Nanorods Decorated with Ag Nanoparticles for Trace Detection of Metronidazole," *RSC Advances* 13, no. 14 (2023): 9732–9748, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3RA01134H>.
63. Z. Wu, J. Liu, Z. Wang, et al., "Nanosphere Lithography-Enabled Hybrid Ag-Cu Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy Substrates with Enhanced Absorption of Excitation Light," *Biosensors* 13, no. 8 (2023): 825, <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios13080825>.
64. J. Krajczewski, E. Dumiszewska, D. Czolak, S. Turczyniak Surdacka, and A. Kudelski, "New, Epitaxial Approach to SERS Platform Preparation – InP Nanowires Coated by an Au Layer as a New, Highly Active, and Stable SERS Platform," *Applied Surface Science* 607 (2023): 155096, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2022.155096>.
65. H. Le Thi Minh, A. T. Nguyen, K. H. Thuy Doan, N. Van Ho Phan, C. M. Chi, and H. Le Vu Tuan, "Optimizing the Structure of Zinc Oxide

- Thin Films and Silver Nanoparticles for Preparing High-Performance and Stability SERS Substrate to Detect Banned Antibiotics in Aquaculture,” *ACS Applied Optical Materials* 1, no. 8 (2023): 1460–1473, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaom.3c00197>.
66. D. Sulaiman, A. M. Alwan, and W. K. Hamoudi, “Pesticide Detection Optimization of Plasmonics Gold Nanoparticles/Silicon Nano-Columns Structures by Controlling the Coupling Lasers Power Density,” *Gold Bulletin* 56, no. 1 (2023): 9–21, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13404-022-00323-x>.
67. H. Guo, X. Ren, X. Song, and X. Li, “Preparation of SiO₂@Ag@ molecular Imprinted Polymers Hybrid for Sensitive and Selective Detection of Amoxicillin Using Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering,” *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy* 291 (2023): 122365, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2023.122365>.
68. L. Xiao, S. Feng, M. Z. Hua, and X. Lu, “Rapid Determination of Thiram on Apple Using a Flexible Bacterial Cellulose-Based SERS Substrate,” *Talanta* 254 (2023): 124128, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2022.124128>.
69. M. A. Zajac, B. Budner, M. Liszewska, et al., “SERS Performance of GaN/Ag Substrates Fabricated by Ag Coating of GaN Platforms,” *Beilstein Journal of Nanotechnology* 14, no. 1 (2023): 552–564, <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjnano.14.46>.
70. M. Kadir, R. Nemkayeva, G. Baigarinova, B. Alpysbayeva, A. Assembayeva, and V. Smirnov, “SERS-Active Substrates Based on Ag-Coated TiO₂ Nanotubes and Nanograss,” *Physica E: Low-dimensional Systems and Nanostructures* 145 (2023): 115499, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physe.2022.115499>.
71. F. Selimoğlu and M. E. Ayhan, “Silver Nanoparticle Decorated Graphene-Based SERS Electrode towards Procalcitonin Detection,” *Vibrational Spectroscopy* 126 (2023): 103539, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vibspec.2023.103539>.
72. M. Matamoros-Ambrocio, E. Sánchez-Mora, and E. Gómez-Barojas, “Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) Substrates Based on Ag-Nanoparticles and Ag-Nanoparticles/Poly (Methyl Methacrylate) Composites,” *Polymers* 15, no. 12 (2023): 2624, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15122624>.
73. B. N. Khlebtsov, A. M. Burov, S. V. Zarkov, and N. G. Khlebtsov, “Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering from Au Nanorods, Nanotriangles, and Nanostars with Tuned Plasmon Resonances,” *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* 25, no. 45 (2023): 30903–30913, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3CP04541B>.
74. X. Zhang, K. Zhao, X. Wang, et al., “Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy for Environmental Monitoring Using Gold Clusters Anchored on Reduced Graphene Oxide,” *Science of the Total Environment* 856 (2023): 158879, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158879>.
75. H. Ma, X. Tang, Y. Liu, et al., “Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering for Direct Protein Function Investigation: Controlled Immobilization and Orientation,” *Analytical Chemistry* 91, no. 14 (2019): 8767–8771, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.9b01956>.
76. X. X. Han, R. S. Rodriguez, C. L. Haynes, Y. Ozaki, and B. Zhao, “Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy,” *Nature Reviews Methods Primers* 1, no. 1 (2022): 1–17, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-021-00083-6>.
77. A. Jaworska, L. E. Jamieson, K. Malek, et al., “SERS-Based Monitoring of the Intracellular pH in Endothelial Cells: The Influence of the Extracellular Environment and Tumour Necrosis Factor- α ,” *Analyst* 140, no. 7 (2015): 2321–2329, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4AN01988A>.
78. J. R. Lakowicz, ed., *Principles of Fluorescence Spectroscopy* (Boston, MA: Springer US, 2006), <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-46312-4>.
79. I. Ragheb, M. Braik, S. Lau-Truong, et al., “Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering on Regular Arrays of Gold Nanostructures: Impact of Long-Range Interactions and the Surrounding Medium,” *Nanomaterials (Basel)* 10, no. 11 (2020): 2201, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10112201>.
80. E. Pensa, E. Cortés, G. Corthey, et al., “The Chemistry of the Sulfur–Gold Interface: In Search of a Unified Model,” *Accounts of Chemical Research* 45, no. 8 (2012): 1183–1192, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ar200260p>.
81. G. Yang and G. Liu, “New Insights for Self-Assembled Monolayers of Organothiols on Au(111) Revealed by Scanning Tunneling Microscopy,” *Journal of Physical Chemistry. B* 107, no. 34 (2003): 8746–8759, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp0219810>.
82. GuideChem, “4-Mercaptobenzoic Acid,” accessed October 25, 2024, <https://www.guideschem.com/encyclopedia/4-mercaptobenzoic-acid-dic7809.html>.
83. P. Ji, Z. Mao, Z. Wang, et al., “Improved Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering Properties of ZrO₂ Nanoparticles by Zn Doping,” *Nanomaterials (Basel)* 9, no. 7 (2019): 983, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano9070983>.
84. S. L. Kleinman, B. Sharma, M. G. Blaber, et al., “Structure Enhancement Factor Relationships in Single Gold Nanoantennas by Surface-Enhanced Raman Excitation Spectroscopy,” *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 135, no. 1 (2013): 301–308, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja309300d>.
85. A.-I. Henry, T. W. Ueltschi, M. O. McAnally, and R. P. V. Duyne, “Spiers Memorial Lecture,” *Faraday Discussions* 205 (2017): 9–30, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7FD00181A>.
86. S. Yang, M. Wang, M. Zou, Q. Sheng, R. Cui, and S. Chen, “Gas Transport Law in Inorganic Nanopores Considering the Influence of Cross Section Shape and Roughness,” *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals* 175 (2023): 114053, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2023.114053>.
87. S. Yang, M. Liang, B. Yu, and M. Zou, “Permeability Model for Fractal Porous Media with Rough Surfaces,” *Microfluidics and Nanofluidics* 18, no. 5–6 (2015): 1085–1093, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10404-014-1500-1>.
88. D.-F. Yang, C. P. Wilde, and M. Morin, “Electrochemical Desorption and Adsorption of Nonyl Mercaptan at Gold Single Crystal Electrode Surfaces,” *Langmuir* 12, no. 26 (1996): 6570–6577, <https://doi.org/10.1021/la960365q>.
89. K. Kolwas and A. Derkachova, “Impact of the Interband Transitions in Gold and Silver on the Dynamics of Propagating and Localized Surface Plasmons,” *Nanomaterials* 10, no. 7 (2020): 1411, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10071411>.
90. P. G. Etchegoin and E. C. Le Ru, “Resolving Single Molecules in Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering within the Inhomogeneous Broadening of Raman Peaks,” *Analytical Chemistry* 82, no. 7 (2010): 2888–2892, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac9028888>.
91. C. Kuttner, R. P. M. Höller, M. Quintanilla, et al., “SERS and Plasmonic Heating Efficiency from Anisotropic Core/Satellite Superstructures,” *Nanoscale* 11, no. 38 (2019): 17655–17663, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9NR06102A>.
92. G. Kang, M. Yang, M. S. Mattei, G. C. Schatz, and R. P. Van Duyne, “In Situ Nanoscale Redox Mapping Using Tip-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy,” *Nano Letters* 19, no. 3 (2019): 2106–2113, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.9b00313>.

Supporting Information

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